

Vaccines and Biologics injury table based on mechanistic evidence – Feb 2020 Covering over 125 conditions

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Injecting a viral or bacterial protein, trains the immune system to recognize the organism and attack it upon subsequent exposure. Thus protecting against disease. Vaccines however have a fundamental flaw. They contain numerous unrelated proteins used for growing the virus/bacteria, as excipients and as contaminants. Such proteins include food, animal, fungal, non-target viral/bacterial and aeroallergen proteins. These proteins are similar to many human proteins. 293 chicken proteins were identified in the influenza vaccine, for example (1). Similarly, animal proteins such as actin and vimentin were identified in the Priorix Tetra vaccine (2). Cow's milk proteins were identified in the DTaP/Tdap vaccines (3). The result is numerous off-target immune responses that attack various parts of the human body (autoimmunity (4–7)) and harmless environmental, food, fungal and commensal bacterial proteins, resulting in a variety of new man-made diseases many of which have not even been discovered. We are therefore discovering new diseases every day. The injuries/diseases described in this document therefore are only a subset of vaccine-induced injuries/diseases and will need constant updates. Bovine proteins in vaccines, causing autoimmunity in dogs has been known for 20 years (8).

Further, off-target immune responses may not result in overt clinical illness. Subclinical illnesses may make the body's processes suboptimal and shave decades off a person's life. Or, a person may suffer an illness that is vaccine-induced but not yet linked to a vaccine.

Most medical research findings are false (9,10) and are affected by flagrant conflicts of interest (11–13). Peer review is broken. (14–16) Most medical findings are based on epidemiological studies that are weak to start with and worse, scientists misinterpret the statistics thus resulting in type II errors. (17) Therefore, as the Institute of Medicine (now known as the National Academy of Medicine) found, most vaccine safety claims based on epidemiological studies are invalid. The National Vaccine Injury Compensation Program's Vaccine Injury Table (18) has only a small set of injuries based on these flawed studies. This document provides a more comprehensive table of vaccine injuries based on mechanistic evidence, which reflects reality.

The US Institute of Medicine (IOM) committee in their 2011 report (19) on Adverse Effects of Vaccines: Evidence and Causality wrote:

“The committee concluded the evidence convincingly supports 14 specific vaccine–adverse event relationships. In all but one of these relationships, the conclusion was based on strong mechanistic evidence with the epidemiologic evidence rated as either limited confidence or insufficient.”

So in an overwhelming 93% (13 of 14) cases, mechanistic studies provided convincing evidence and epidemiological studies failed to do so. Epidemiological studies have numerous sources of confounding and offer little value. Therefore, this document is mainly based on mechanistic evidence of injuries caused by vaccines and biologics.

Any vaccine can be contaminated with ingredients normally used in any other vaccine. Therefore there is a possibility that **any** vaccine can cause **any** of the diseases listed below. The US National Academy of Medicine (NAM) has documented that there are no regulations or labeling laws that govern such

contamination. Therefore, vaccines contain numerous food proteins such as peanut, sesame, soy, milk, egg, gelatin, fish etc., for example, which are not always declared. (20)

When the ingredient that can cause the disease is declared or is likely to be present in the vaccine even without contamination, then the disease risk is higher. Such vaccines are listed under each disease.

The US Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) is required by law to continuously improve vaccine safety and provide a report of such improvements to Congress, every two years. The HHS admitted providing no such report and thus repeatedly broke the law for 30 years. (21)

The vaccine ingredients are derived from the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) (22).

The CDC knows the dangers of these ingredients and are therefore now creating new versions of the document with these ingredients missing from them (23). They fraudulently claim that:

“Others are residual trace amounts of materials that were used during the manufacturing process and removed. These can include:

Cell culture materials, used to grow the vaccine antigens. For example, **egg protein**, various culture media.”

They claim the materials were “removed” and provide egg protein as an example. But egg protein is still listed as being present in the final product even in this censored version. So they contradict their own claim of such material being removed from the vaccine. However, they omitted any mention of casein proteins (cow’s milk derived) present in DTap/Tdap vaccines, for example, but we know those are still present in the final vaccine product (3).

List of Vaccines and Biologics

[Vaccine and Biologics induced diseases](#)

Each vaccine link below will transfer to a table of injuries caused by the vaccine.

[A](#) [B](#) [C](#) [D](#) [E](#) [F](#) [H](#) [I](#) [J](#) [M](#) [N](#) [O](#) [P](#) [R](#) [S](#) [T](#) [V](#) [Y](#) [Z](#)

[Adenovirus](#)

[Anthrax \(Biothrax\)](#)

[Cholera \(Vaxchora\)](#)

[DT \(Sanofi\)](#)

DTap ([Daptacel](#))

DTap ([Infanrix](#))

DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#))

DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#))

DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#))

DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#))

[ERBEVO](#) Ebola vaccine

[FIASP](#) (Insulin)

[ActHiB](#)

Hib ([Hiberix](#))

Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#))

Hep A ([Havrix](#))

Hep A ([Vaqta](#))

Hep B ([Engerix-B](#))

Hep B ([Recombivax](#))

Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#))

Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#))

[Humulin-R](#) (Insulin)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#))

Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Influenza ([Fluad](#))

Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Influenza ([Fluvirin](#))

Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent

Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose

Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal

Influenza ([FluMist](#)) Quadrivalent

Insulin injection

FIASP (Insulin)

Humulin-R (Insulin)

LANTUS (Insulin)

MYXREDLIN (Insulin)

Novolin (R, 70/30 Insulin)

Novolog (Insulin)

Vaccines and Biologics list

Disease list

Japanese Encephalitis (Ixiaro)

Meningococcal (MenACWY-Menactra)

Meningococcal (MenACWY-Menveo)

Meningococcal (MenB – Bexsero)

Meningococcal (MenB – Trumenba)

MMR (MMR-II)

MMRV (ProQuad)

MYXREDLIN (Insulin)

Novolin (R, 70/30 Insulin)

Novolog (Insulin)

OZEMPIC injection

Vaccines and Biologics list

Disease list

Pneumococcal (PCV13 – Prevnar 13)

Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – Pneumovax)

Polio (IPV – Ipol)

Rabies ([Imovax](#))

Rabies ([RabAvert](#))

Rotavirus ([RotaTeq](#))

Rotavirus ([Rotarix](#))

[Smallpox](#) (Vaccinia) (ACAM2000)

Td ([Tenivac](#))

Td ([Mass Biologics](#))

Tdap ([Adacel](#))

Tdap ([Boostrix](#))

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Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#))

Typhoid ([Vivotif Ty21a](#))

Varicella ([Varivax](#))

[Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax)

Zoster (Shingles) ([Zostavax](#))

Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

[Biologics](#)

[Insulin](#) injection

[OZEMPIC](#) injection

Vaccine-induced diseases

[List of vaccines](#) and biologics

Each link below will transfer to a list of vaccines that can cause this disease. All diseases listed here are part of GAVIDOTTIR (GAMut of Vaccine Induced Damage emphasizing Off Target Immune Responses) (24).

[A](#) [B](#) [C](#) [D](#) [E](#) [F](#) [G](#) [H](#) [I](#) [J](#) [K](#) [L](#) [M](#) [N](#) [O](#) [P](#) [R](#) [S](#) [T](#) [U](#) [V](#) [W](#) [Y](#)

[Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis](#)

[Acute lymphocytic leukemia](#)

[Acute myeloid leukemia](#)

[Acquired epidermolysis bullosa](#)

[Addison's disease](#)

[Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder \(ADHD\)](#)

[Alopecia areata](#)

[Alzheimer's](#)

[Ankylosing spondylitis](#)

[Antiphospholipid syndrome](#)

[Asthma/Rhinitis/seasonal allergies/Pet allergies/GERD/Osteoporosis/Chronic Kidney Disease](#)

[Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease](#)

[Atopic dermatitis](#)

[Autism](#)

[Maternal antibody related autism](#)

[Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism](#)

[Maternal glutamate receptor antibody related autism](#)

[Autoimmune cardiomyopathy](#)

[Autoimmune diseases](#)

[Autoimmune gastritis](#)

[Autoimmune glomerulonephritis](#)

[Autoimmune hemolytic anemia](#)

[Autoimmune hepatitis](#)

[Autoimmune neuropathy](#)

[Autoimmune optic neuritis](#)

[Autoimmune pancreatitis](#)

[Autoimmune peripheral neuropathy](#)

[Autoimmune polyendocrine syndrome](#)

[Autoimmune thrombocytic purpura](#)

[Autoimmune thyroiditis](#)

[Autoimmune uveitis](#)

[Autoimmune vasculitis](#)

[Blood brain barrier \(BBB\) disruption](#)

[Bullous pemphigoid](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

[Cardiac arrhythmia](#)

[Celiac disease](#)

[Central nervous system vasculitis](#)

[Cerebral infarction](#)

[Chronic fatigue syndrome](#)

[Chronic Kidney Disease](#)

[Chronic lymphocytic leukemia](#)

[Cicatrical pemphigoid](#)

[Corn allergy](#)

[Crohn's disease](#)

[Chronic lymphocytic leukemia](#)

[Cutaneous lupus erythematosus](#)

[Demyelinating polyneuropathy](#)

[Dermatitis herpetiformis](#)

[Dermatomyositis](#)

[Diabetes mellitus](#)

[Egg allergy](#)

[Encephalitis](#)

[Epilepsy](#)

[Felty's syndrome](#)

[Fibromyalgia](#)

[Food allergy](#)

[Gastric cancer](#)

[Gelatin allergy](#)

[GERD \(Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease\)](#)

[Giant cell arteritis](#)

[Glioma](#)

[Goodpasture syndrome](#)

[Granulomatosis with polyangiitis](#)

[Graves' disease](#)

[Guillain-Barre syndrome \(GBS\)](#)

Vaccines and Biologics list

Disease list

Hirata disease

Hypothyroidism

Immune thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP)

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD)

Influenza shock syndrome (ISS)

Intussusception

Juvenile ankylosing spondylitis

Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis

Kawasaki disease

Lambert-Eaton myasthenic syndrome

Lichen planus

Maternal antibody related autism

Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism

Maternal glutamate receptor antibody related autism

Membranous Nephropathy

Milk Allergy

Miller-Fisher syndrome

Mixed connective tissue disease

Multiple sclerosis

Myasthenia Gravis

Narcolepsy

Neurodegenerative disorders

Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD)

Neuropsychiatric disorders

Obesity

Osteoarthritis

Osteoporosis

Optic Ischemic Neuropathy

Pemphigus

Pemphigus gestationis

Pet allergies

Polyarteritis nodosa

Polycystic ovarian syndrome

[Polymyalgia rheumatica](#)
[Primary biliary cirrhosis](#)
[Primary thrombocytopenia](#)
[Psoriasis](#)
[Psoriatic arthritis](#)

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[Raynaud disease](#)
[Reactive arthritis](#)
[Relapsing polychondritis](#)
[Rheumatic myocarditis](#)
[Rheumatoid arthritis](#)
[Rhinitis](#)
[Rice Allergy](#)

[Sarcoidosis](#)
[Scleroderma](#)
[Sclerosing cholangitis](#)
[Seasonal Allergies](#)
[Shingles](#)
[Sjogren's syndrome](#)
[Soy allergy](#)
[Stiff-person syndrome](#)
[Sudden infant death syndrome \(SIDS\)](#)
[Systemic lupus erythematosus \(SLE\)](#)
[Systemic scleroderma](#)

[Temporal arteritis](#)
[Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura](#)
[Type 1 diabetes \(T1D\)](#)

[Ulcerative colitis](#)
[Uveitis](#)

[Vasculitis](#)
[Vitiligo](#)
[Vogt-Koyanagi-Harada disease](#)

[Wheat allergy](#)

[Yellow fever vaccine-associated viscerotropic disease](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Adenovirus

Ingredient	Disease
Lactose derived from cow's milk is contaminated with cow's milk proteins. Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune disease and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
human-diploid fibroblast cell cultures (strain WI-38), Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium, fetal bovine serum, sodium bicarbonate, monosodium glutamate, sucrose, D-mannose, Dfructose, dextrose, human serum albumin, potassium phosphate, plasdone C, anhydrous lactose, microcrystalline cellulose, polacrilin potassium, magnesium stearate, cellulose acetate phthalate, alcohol, acetone, castor oil, FD&C Yellow #6 aluminum lake dye	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Anthrax (Biothrax)

Ingredient	Disease
Lactose derived from cow's milk is contaminated with cow's milk proteins. Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
amino acids, vitamins, inorganic salts, sugars, aluminum hydroxide, sodium chloride, benzethonium chloride, formaldehyde BCG (Tice) glycerin, asparagine, citric acid, potassium phosphate, magnesium sulfate, iron ammonium citrate, lactose	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Cholera (Vaxchora)

Ingredient	Disease
casamino acids, yeast extract, mineral salts, anti-foaming agent, ascorbic acid, hydrolyzed casein, sodium chloride, sucrose, dried lactose, sodium bicarbonate, sodium carbonate	Oral vaccine. So the effects of these ingredients are different compared to injected vaccines and have not yet been investigated.

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

DT (Sanofi)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> and <i>C. tetani</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
aluminum phosphate, isotonic sodium chloride, formaldehyde, casein, cystine, maltose, uracil, inorganic salts, vitamins, dextrose	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

DTap (Daptacel)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> and <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
aluminum phosphate, formaldehyde, glutaraldehyde, 2-phenoxyethanol, Stainer-Scholte medium, casamino acids, dimethyl-beta-cyclodextrin, Mueller's growth medium, ammonium sulfate, modified Mueller-Miller casamino acid medium without beef heart infusion	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

DTap (Infanrix)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> and <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
Fenton medium containing a bovine extract, modified Latham medium derived from bovine casein, formaldehyde, modified Stainer-Scholte liquid medium, glutaraldehyde, aluminum hydroxide, sodium chloride	

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DTap IPV (Kinrix)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins, VERO cells	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> and <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
Fenton medium containing a bovine extract, modified Latham medium derived from bovine casein, formaldehyde, modified Stainer-Scholte liquid medium, glutaraldehyde, aluminum hydroxide, VERO cells, a continuous line of monkey kidney cells, Calf serum, lactalbumin hydrolysate, sodium chloride, neomycin sulfate, polymyxin B	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

DTap IPV (Quadracel)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> and <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
modified Mueller's growth medium, ammonium sulfate, modified Mueller-Miller casamino acid medium without beef heart infusion, formaldehyde, aluminum phosphate, Stainer Scholte medium, casamino acids, dimethyl-beta-cyclodextrin, MRC-5 cells, normal human diploid cells, CMRL 1969 medium supplemented with calf serum, Medium 199 without calf serum, 2-phenoxyethanol, polysorbate 80, glutaraldehyde, neomycin, polymyxin B sulfate	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

DTap HepB IPV (Pediatrix)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins, VERO cells	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Yeast protein	Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> , <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins and Hepatitis B surface antigen	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
Fenton medium containing a bovine extract, modified Latham medium derived from bovine casein, formaldehyde, glutaraldehyde, modified Stainer-Scholte liquid medium, VERO cells, a continuous line of monkey kidney cells, calf serum and lactalbumin hydrolysate, aluminum hydroxide, aluminum phosphate, aluminum salts, sodium chloride, polysorbate 80 (Tween 80)	

neomycin sulfate, polymyxin B, yeast protein.	
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[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

DTap IPV/Hib (Pentacel)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> , <i>H. influenzae</i> and <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
aluminum phosphate, polysorbate 80, sucrose, formaldehyde, glutaraldehyde, bovine serum albumin, 2-phenoxyethanol, neomycin, polymyxin B sulfate, modified Mueller's growth medium, ammonium sulfate, modified Mueller-Miller casamino acid medium without beef heart infusion, Stainer-Scholte medium, casamino acids, dimethyl-beta-cyclodextrin. MRC-5 cells (a line of normal human diploid cells), CMRL 1969 medium supplemented	

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ERBEVO

Ingredient	Disease
VERO cell proteins (a continuous line of African green monkey kidney cells), Vesicular Stomatitis Virus (VSV) proteins, Zaire ebolavirus envelope glycoprotein	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Rice proteins	Rice Allergy

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ActHiB

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
<i>H. Influenzae</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
sodium chloride, modified Mueller and Miller medium (the culture medium contains milk derived raw materials [casein derivatives]), formaldehyde, sucrose	

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[Disease list](#)

Hib (Hiberix)

Ingredient	Disease
<i>H. Influenzae</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
Lactose derived from cow's milk is contaminated with cow's milk proteins. Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
saline, synthetic medium, formaldehyde, sodium chloride, lactose	

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Hib (PedvaxHIB)

Ingredient	Disease
<i>H. Influenzae</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism , Alopecia areata
complex fermentation media, amorphous aluminum hydroxyphosphate sulfate, sodium chloride	

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Hep A (Havrix)

Ingredient	Disease
Hepatitis A proteins	Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS)
polysorbate 20	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
MRC-5 human diploid cells, formalin, aluminum hydroxide, amino acid supplement, phosphate-buffered saline solution, neomycin sulfate, aminoglycoside antibiotic	

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Hep A (Vaqta)

Ingredient	Disease
Hepatitis A proteins	Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS)
Bovine albumin	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
MRC-5 diploid fibroblasts, amorphous aluminum hydroxyphosphate sulfate, non-viral protein, DNA, formaldehyde, neomycin, sodium borate, sodium chloride	

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Hep B (Engerix-B)

Ingredient	Disease
Yeast protein	Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
aluminum hydroxide, sodium chloride, disodium phosphate dihydrate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate dihydrate	

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Hep B (Recombivax)

Ingredient	Disease
Yeast protein	Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
soy peptone	Soy Allergy , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
dextrose, amino acids, mineral salts, phosphate buffer, formaldehyde, potassium aluminum sulfate, amorphous aluminum hydroxyphosphate sulfate	

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Hep B (Heplisav-B)

Ingredient	Disease
Yeast protein	Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
vitamins and mineral salts, yeast DNA, deoxycholate, phosphorothioate linked oligodeoxynucleotide, phosphate buffered saline, sodium phosphate, dibasic dodecahydrate, monobasic dehydrate	

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Hep A/Hep B (Twinrix)

Ingredient	Disease
Yeast protein	Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
MRC-5 human diploid cells, formalin, aluminum phosphate, aluminum hydroxide, amino acids, sodium chloride, phosphate buffer, neomycin sulfate	

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Human Papillomavirus (HPV) (Gardasil 9)

Ingredient	Disease
Yeast protein	Atopic dermatitis , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
vitamins, amino acids, mineral salts, carbohydrates, amorphous aluminum hydroxyphosphate sulfate, sodium chloride, L-histidine, sodium borate	

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Influenza (Afluria) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Ingredient	Disease
Egg proteins	Egg allergy
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
sodium chloride, monobasic sodium phosphate, dibasic sodium phosphate, monobasic potassium phosphate, potassium chloride, calcium chloride, sodium taurodeoxycholate, sucrose, neomycin sulfate, polymyxin B, beta-propiolactone, thimerosal (multidose vials)	

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Influenza (Fluad)

Ingredient	Disease
Egg proteins	Egg allergy
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
squalene, sorbitan trioleate, sodium citrate dehydrate, citric acid monohydrate, neomycin, kanamycin, barium, egg proteins, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), formaldehyde	

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Influenza (Fluarix) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Ingredient	Disease
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Egg proteins	Egg allergy
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
octoxynol-10 (TRITON X-100), α -tocopheryl hydrogen succinate, hydrocortisone, gentamicin sulfate, formaldehyde, sodium deoxycholate, sodium phosphate-buffered isotonic sodium chloride	

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Influenza (Flublok) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Ingredient	Disease
Polysorbate 20	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Baculovirus and Spodoptera frugiperda cell proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) High risk as Flublok contains 3X viral proteins as a regular influenza vaccine. (20)
sodium chloride, monobasic sodium phosphate, dibasic sodium phosphate, baculovirus and cellular DNA, Triton X-100, lipids, vitamins, amino acids, mineral salts	

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Influenza (Flucelvax) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Ingredient	Disease
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Madin Darby Canine Kidney (MDCK) cell protein, protein other than HA	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS)
MDCK cell DNA, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, and β -propiolactone	

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Influenza (Flulaval) Trivalent & Quadrivalent

Ingredient	Disease
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Egg proteins	Egg allergy
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
formaldehyde, sodium deoxycholate, α -tocopheryl hydrogen succinate, thimerosal (multi-dose vials)	

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Influenza (Fluvirin)

Ingredient	Disease
Egg proteins	Egg allergy
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
polymyxin, neomycin, betapropiolactone, nonylphenol ethoxylate, thimerosal	

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Influenza (Fluzone) Quadrivalent

Ingredient	Disease
Egg protein	Egg allergy
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Formaldehyde, octylphenol ethoxylate (Triton X-100), sodium phosphate buffered isotonic sodium chloride solution, thimerosal (multi-dose vials), sucrose	

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Influenza (Fluzone) High Dose

Ingredient	Disease
Egg protein	Egg allergy
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
octylphenol ethoxylate (Triton X-100), sodium phosphate-buffered isotonic sodium chloride solution, formaldehyde, sucrose	

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Influenza (Fluzone) Intradermal

Ingredient	Disease
Egg protein	Egg allergy
Influenza proteins	Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS) , Kawasaki disease , Guillain-Barré Syndrome (GBS) , Narcolepsy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
formaldehyde, octylphenol ethoxylate (Triton X-100), sodium phosphate buffered isotonic sodium chloride solution, sucrose	

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Influenza (FluMist) Quadrivalent

Ingredient	Disease
monosodium glutamate, arginine, sucrose, dibasic potassium phosphate, monobasic potassium phosphate, ovalbumin, gentamicin sulfate, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)	Nasal spray vaccine. So the effects of these ingredients are different compared to injected vaccines and have not yet been investigated.

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Insulin (FIASP, Novolin R, 70/30, Novolog, MYXREDLIN), OZEMPIC injection

Ingredient	Disease
Yeast protein	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)

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Insulin (LANTUS, Humulin-R)

Ingredient	Disease
<i>E. coli</i> residual proteins	Inflammatory bowel disease

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Japanese Encephalitis (Ixiaro)

Ingredient	Disease
bovine serum albumin, host cell protein	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
aluminum hydroxide, protamine sulfate, formaldehyde, bovine serum albumin, host cell DNA, sodium metabisulphite, host cell protein	

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Meningococcal (MenACWY-Menactra)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
N. meningitidis residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Watson Scherp media containing casamino acid, modified culture medium containing hydrolyzed casein, ammonium sulfate, sodium phosphate, formaldehyde, sodium chloride	

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Meningococcal (MenACWY-Menveo)

Ingredient	Disease
Yeast extract	Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
N. meningitidis residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
formaldehyde, amino acids, Franz complete medium, CY medium	

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Meningococcal (MenB – Bexsero)

Ingredient	Disease
<i>E. coli</i> residual proteins	Inflammatory bowel disease
N. meningitidis residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
aluminum hydroxide, histidine, sucrose, deoxycholate, kanamycin	

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Meningococcal (MenB – Trumenba)

Ingredient	Disease
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer’s , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
N. meningitidis residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn’s disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
defined fermentation growth media, aluminum phosphate, histidine buffered saline	

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MMR (MMR-II)

Ingredient	Disease
Chick embryo cell culture	Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD) , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
fetal bovine serum, hydrolyzed gelatin	Gelatin allergy , Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn’s disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Live virus	Encephalitis
Measles virus	Sub-acute Sclerosing Panencephalitis (SSPE)
Measles viral proteins	Kawasaki disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
WI-38 human diploid lung fibroblasts, vitamins, amino acids, sucrose, glutamate, recombinant human albumin, neomycin, sorbitol, sodium phosphate, sodium chloride	

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MMRV (ProQuad)

Ingredient	Disease
Chick embryo cell culture	Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD) , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Bovine calf serum, hydrolyzed gelatin	Gelatin allergy , Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Live virus	Encephalitis
Measles virus	Sub-acute Sclerosing Panencephalitis (SSPE)
Measles viral proteins	Kawasaki disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
Varicella virus	Glioma , Shingles
WI-38 human diploid lung fibroblasts, MRC-5 cells, sucrose, sodium chloride, sorbitol, monosodium L-glutamate, sodium phosphate dibasic, human albumin, sodium bicarbonate, potassium phosphate monobasic, potassium chloride; potassium phosphate dibasic, neomycin	

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Pneumococcal (PCV13 – Prevnar 13)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
soy peptone	Soy Allergy , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders .
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Yeast protein	Atopic dermatitis , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Vitiligo , Narcolepsy , Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , Rheumatoid arthritis , Alzheimer's , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
<i>S. pneumoniae</i> , <i>C. diphtheriae</i> residual proteins	Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
soy peptone broth, casamino acids and yeast extract-based medium, CRM197 carrier protein, polysorbate 80, succinate buffer, aluminum phosphate	

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Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – Pneumovax)

Ingredient	Disease
<i>S. pneumoniae</i> residual proteins	Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
phenol	

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Polio (IPV – Ipol)

Ingredient	Disease
Calf bovine serum, VERO cells (a continuous line of monkey kidney cells)	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Eagle MEM modified medium, calf bovine serum, M-199 without calf bovine serum, vero cells (a continuous line of monkey kidney cells), phenoxyethanol, formaldehyde, neomycin, streptomycin, polymyxin B	

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Rabies (Imovax)

Ingredient	Disease
human albumin, neomycin sulfate, phenol red indicator, MRC-5 human diploid cells, betapropriolactone	The effects of these ingredients have not yet been investigated.

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Rabies (RabAvert)

Ingredient	Disease
Chicken fibroblasts	Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD) , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Bovine serum, gelatin	Gelatin allergy , Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Egg proteins	Egg allergy
chicken fibroblasts, β -propiolactone, polygeline (processed bovine gelatin), human serum albumin, bovine serum, potassium glutamate, sodium EDTA, ovalbumin, neomycin, chlortetracycline, amphotericin B	

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Rotavirus (RotaTeq)

Ingredient	Disease
sucrose, sodium citrate, sodium phosphate monobasic monohydrate, sodium hydroxide, polysorbate 80, cell culture media, fetal bovine serum, vero cells [DNA from porcine circoviruses (PCV) 1 and 2 has been detected in RotaTeq. PCV-1 and PCV-2 are not known to cause disease in humans.]	Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Intussusception

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Rotavirus (Rotarix)

Ingredient	Disease
Vero cells, dextran, Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (sodium chloride, potassium chloride, magnesium sulfate, ferric (III) nitrate, sodium phosphate, sodium pyruvate, Dglucose, concentrated vitamin solution, L-cystine, L-tyrosine, amino acids solution, Lglutamine, calcium chloride, sodium hydrogenocarbonate, and phenol red), sorbitol, sucrose, calcium carbonate, sterile water, xanthan [Porcine circovirus type 1 (PCV-1) is present in Rotarix. PCV-1 is not known to cause disease in humans.]	Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Intussusception

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Smallpox (Vaccinia) (ACAM2000)

Ingredient	Disease
African Green Monkey kidney (Vero) cells	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
African Green Monkey kidney (Vero) cells, HEPES, 2% human serum albumin, 0.7% sodium chloride USP, 5% Mannitol USP, neomycin, polymyxin B, 50% Glycerin USP, 0.25% phenol USP	

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Td (Tenivac)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) Protein	Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related, Autism, Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease, Cerebral infarction, Diabetes mellitus, Obesity, Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer, Vitiligo, Autism, Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), Crohn's disease, Type 1 diabetes (T1D), Membranous Nephropathy
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> and <i>C. tetani</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease, Cardiac arrhythmia, Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), Hypothyroidism, Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease, Cerebral infarction, Diabetes mellitus, Obesity, Crohn's disease, Type 1 diabetes (T1D), Maternal antibody related autism
aluminum phosphate, formaldehyde, modified Mueller-Miller casamino acid medium without beef heart infusion, ammonium sulfate, sodium chloride, water	

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Td (Mass Biologics)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) Protein	Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> and <i>C. tetani</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
aluminum phosphate, formaldehyde, thimerosal, modified Mueller's media which contains bovine extracts, ammonium sulfate	

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Tdap (Adacel)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) Protein	Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> and <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
aluminum phosphate, formaldehyde, 2-phenoxyethanol, Stainer-Scholte medium, casamino acids, dimethyl-beta-cyclodextrin, glutaraldehyde, modified Mueller-Miller casamino acid medium without beef heart infusion, ammonium sulfate, modified Mueller's growth medium	

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Tdap (Boostrix)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) Protein	Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Autism , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
<i>C. diphtheriae</i> , <i>C. tetani</i> and <i>B. pertussis</i> residual proteins	Kawasaki disease , Cardiac arrhythmia , Maternal antibody related autism , Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) , Hypothyroidism , Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Maternal antibody related autism
modified Latham medium derived from bovine casein, Fenton medium containing a bovine extract, formaldehyde, modified Stainer-Scholte liquid medium, glutaraldehyde, aluminum hydroxide, sodium chloride, polysorbate 80	

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Typhoid (Typhim Vi)

Ingredient	Disease
Bovine folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein	Autism , Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism , Cerebral Folate Deficiency Syndrome
Bovine casein	Milk Allergy
Bovine insulin	Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Bovine adiponectin	Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease , Cerebral infarction , Diabetes mellitus , Obesity , Polycystic ovarian syndrome
Bovine proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Casein, decyltrimethylammonium bromide, formaldehyde, phenol, polydimethylsiloxane, disodium phosphate, monosodium phosphate, semi-synthetic medium, sodium chloride	

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Typhoid (Vivotif Ty21a)

Ingredient	Disease
yeast extract, casein, dextrose, galactose, sucrose, ascorbic acid, amino acids, lactose, magnesium stearate, gelatin	Oral vaccine. So the effects of these ingredients are different compared to injected vaccines and have not yet been investigated.

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Varicella (Varivax)

Ingredient	Disease
Fetal bovine serum, hydrolyzed gelatin	Gelatin allergy , Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Varicella virus	Glioma , Shingles
MRC-5 human diploid cells, including DNA & protein, sucrose, hydrolyzed gelatin, sodium chloride, monosodium L-glutamate, sodium phosphate dibasic, sodium phosphate monobasic, potassium phosphate monobasic, potassium chloride, EDTA, neomycin, fetal bovine serum	

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[Disease list](#)

Yellow Fever (YF-Vax)

Ingredient	Disease
Gelatin	Gelatin allergy , Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)
Egg protein	Egg allergy
Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever vaccine-associated viscerotropic disease
sorbitol, gelatin, sodium chloride, egg protein	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Zoster (Shingles) (Zostavax)

Ingredient	Disease
hydrolyzed porcine gelatin, bovine calf serum	Gelatin allergy , Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Membranous Nephropathy
Egg protein	Egg allergy
MRC-5 human diploid cells, including DNA & protein, sucrose, hydrolyzed porcine gelatin, sodium chloride, monosodium L-glutamate, sodium phosphate dibasic, potassium phosphate monobasic, potassium chloride; neomycin, bovine calf serum	

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[Disease list](#)

Zoster (Shingles) (Shingrix)

Ingredient	Disease
Polysorbate 80	Wheat allergy , Corn allergy , Blood brain barrier disruption , Epilepsy , Fibromyalgia , Neuropsychiatric disorders , Neurodegenerative disorders , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Alzheimer's , Maternal Glutamate receptor antibody related autism , Autoimmune diseases and cancer
Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) cell proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Optic Ischemic Neuropathy , Type 1 diabetes (T1D) , Supraventricular tachyarrhythmia , Supraventricular tachycardia
sucrose, sodium chloride, dioleoyl phosphatidylcholine (DOPC), potassium dihydrogen phosphate, cholesterol, sodium dihydrogen phosphate dihydrate, disodium phosphate anhydrous, dipotassium phosphate, polysorbate 80, <i>Salmonella minnesota</i> and <i>Quillaja saponaria</i> Molina, AS01 _B	

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Biologics

Ingredient	Disease
Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) cell proteins	Autoimmune diseases and cancer , Vitiligo , Autism , Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) , Crohn's disease , Type 1 diabetes (T1D)

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Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)

Chick and animal proteins contained in vaccines can cause GAD65 antibody related ADHD. (4,5,25,26) Polysorbate 80 contained in vaccines can cause the development of NMDA antibody related ADHD. (27,28)

[Adenovirus](#), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), [DTap \(Daptacel\)](#), [DTap \(Infanrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Kinrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Quadracel\)](#), [DTap HepB IPV \(Pediatrix\)](#), [DTap IPV/Hib \(Pentacel\)](#), [ERVEBO Ebola vaccine](#), [Hib \(Hiberix\)](#), [Hep A \(Havrix\)](#), [Hep A \(Vaqta\)](#), [Hep B \(Heplisav-B\)](#), [Hep A/Hep B \(Twinrix\)](#), [Human Papillomavirus \(HPV\) \(Gardasil 9\)](#), [Influenza \(Fluad\)](#), [Influenza \(Fluarix\) Trivalent & Quadrivalent](#), [Influenza \(Flublok\) Trivalent & Quadrivalent](#), [Influenza \(Flucelvax\) Trivalent & Quadrivalent](#), [Influenza \(Flulaval\) Trivalent & Quadrivalent](#), [Japanese Encephalitis \(Ixiaro\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenACWY-Menactra\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenB – Trumenba\)](#), [MMR \(MMR-II\)](#), [MMRV \(ProQuad\)](#), [Pneumococcal \(PCV13 – Prevnar 13\)](#), [Polio \(IPV – Ipol\)](#), [Rabies \(RabAvert\)](#), [Smallpox \(Vaccinia\) \(ACAM2000\)](#), [Td \(Tenivac\)](#), [Td \(Mass Biologics\)](#), [Tdap \(Adacel\)](#), [Tdap \(Boostrix\)](#), [Typhoid \(Typhim Vi\)](#), [Varicella \(Varivax\)](#), [Yellow Fever \(YF-Vax\)](#), [Zoster \(Shingles\) \(Zostavax\)](#), [Zoster \(Shingles\) \(Shingrix\)](#), [Biologics](#)

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Alopecia areata

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *N. meningitidis* and *S. cerevisiae* residual proteins contained in vaccines can cause Alopecia areata due to molecular mimicry to self-antigens. (29)

[DT \(Sanofi\)](#), [DTap \(Daptacel\)](#), [DTap \(Infanrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Kinrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Quadracel\)](#), [DTap HepB IPV \(Pediatrix\)](#), [DTap IPV/Hib \(Pentacel\)](#), [ActHiB](#), [Hib \(Hiberix\)](#), [Hib \(PedvaxHIB\)](#), [Hep B](#)

([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pneumovax](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#))

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Alzheimer's disease

Polysorbate 80 (plant protein derived) contained in vaccines can cause glutamate receptor antibody related Alzheimer's disease. (27) Yeast protein contained in vaccines and insulin injections can cause prion related Alzheimer's disease. (30,31)

DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pneumovax](#) 13), Polio (IPV – [Ipol](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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[Asthma](#), [Rhinitis](#), [seasonal allergies](#), [Pet allergies](#), [Food allergies](#), [Heartburn](#), [Osteoporosis](#) and [Chronic Kidney Disease](#)

All vaccines cause the development of asthma, seasonal allergies, pet allergies (32–34) due to contamination with aeroallergens. All vaccines contain numerous antigens and cause anaphylaxis (19) because of IgE mediated sensitization directed against the same antigen by a previous vaccine. The specific case of food antigens in vaccines results in the development of food allergy (33,35–37).

Since food contains all aeroallergens, once sensitized to aeroallergens, eating food can result in heartburn due to excess stomach acid production (32). Proton-pump inhibitors (PPI) are a commonly prescribed treatment for heartburn. PPI can cause cancer (38,39), chronic kidney disease (CKD) (40) and osteoporosis. These iatrogenic cascade of diseases follow the original vaccine induced iatrogenic injury.

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Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease

Atherosclerosis related coronary artery disease is caused by autoimmunity induced by the following proteins in vaccines. (41,42)

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae*, *C. tetani*, Hepatitis B surface antigen and Influenza A proteins.

[Adenovirus](#), Anthrax ([Biothrax](#)), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [Pevnar 13](#), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar 13](#)), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#))

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Atopic dermatitis

Atopic dermatitis can be caused by yeast proteins (*S. cerevisiae*) in vaccines. (43)

DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), [Pevnar 13](#), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar 13](#))

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Autism

Cow's milk protein (bovine casein, casamino acids, lactose used in vaccine manufacturing are derived from cow's milk) contained in vaccines can cause folate receptor alpha antibody mediated autism. (44) Polysorbate 80 derived from plant proteins can cause glutamate receptor antibody mediated autism. (27) Chick and animal proteins contained in vaccines can cause GAD65 antibody related

autism. (4,5,25,26) A vaccine not approved for children can cause autism by causing fetal damage when administered to the mother, even before conception, by inducing anti-brain antibodies (45).

Vaccines that contain milk derived lactose (46) can also cause the development of autism as above.

Anthrax ([Biothrax](#)), [Adenovirus](#), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [ERVEBO Ebola vaccine](#), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), MMR (MMR-II), MMRV (ProQuad), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Japanese Encephalitis ([Ixiaro](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Prevnar 13](#)), Polio (IPV – [Ipol](#)), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#)), Biologics

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Autoimmune diseases and cancer

Animal, fungal, viral, bacterial and food proteins can have molecular mimicry to human proteins. Immunization with such alien proteins cause numerous autoimmune diseases. When the autoimmune disease target is the carbonic anhydrase protein, it can result in cancer. (4–7,17,26,27,41,44,45,47–65)

Insulin injections contain residual yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) proteins (66–70). This results in the synthesis of Anti-Saccharomyces Cerevisiae Antibodies (ASCA) (71). ASCA cause numerous autoimmune diseases (72).

Vaccine induced autoimmune diseases include the following:

- Acquired epidermolysis bullosa
- Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis
- Alopecia areata
- Alzheimer's disease
- Ankylosing spondylitis
- Antiphospholipid syndrome (APS)
- Arteriosclerosis
- Arteriosclerotic cardiovascular disease
- Autoimmune atherosclerosis
- Autoimmune cardiomyopathy
- Autoimmune gastritis
- Autoimmune glomerulonephritis
- Autoimmune haemolytic anaemia
- Autoimmune hepatitis
- Autoimmune neuropathy
- Autoimmune optic neuritis
- Autoimmune pancreatitis

Autoimmune peripheral neuropathy
Autoimmune polyendocrine syndrome
Autoimmune polyendocrine syndrome type 1
Autoimmune thrombocytopenic purpura
Autoimmune thyroiditis
Autoimmune uveitis
Autoimmune vasculitis
Bullous pemphigoid
Celiac disease

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Central nervous system vasculitis
Chronic fatigue syndrome
Cicatrical pemphigoid
Crohn's disease
Cutaneous lupus erythematosus
Demyelinating polyneuropathy
Dermatitis herpetiformis
Felty's syndrome
Giant cell arteritis
Goodpasture's syndrome
Granulomatosis with polyangiitis
Graves' disease
Guillain-Barre syndrome
Hirata disease
Hypothyroidism
Immune thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP)
Inflammatory bowel disease
Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (Type 1 diabetes)
Juvenile ankylosing spondylitis
Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis
Kawasaki disease

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Lambert-Eaton myasthenic syndrome
Lichen planus
Lupus erythematosus
Miller Fisher syndrome
Mixed connective tissue disease (MCTD)
Multiple sclerosis
Myasthenia gravis
Narcolepsy
Neuromyelitis optica
Osteoarthritis

Optic Ischemic Neuropathy
 Pemphigus
 Pemphigus gestationis
 Polyarteritis nodosa
 Polymyalgia rheumatica
 Primary biliary cirrhosis
 Primary thrombocytopenia
 Psoriasis
 Psoriatic arthritis
 Raynaud's disease
 Reactive arthritis
 Relapsing polychondritis
 Rheumatic myocarditis
 Rheumatoid arthritis
 Rheumatologic disorder
 Sarcoidosis
 Scleroderma
 Sclerosing cholangitis
 Sjogren's syndrome
 Stiff-person syndrome
 Systemic lupus erythematosus
 Systemic scleroderma
 Temporal arteritis
 Ulcerative colitis
 Uveitis
 Vasculitis
 Vitiligo
 Vogt-Koyanagi-Harada

Any vaccine that causes autoimmune diseases can cause the induction of autoimmune responses against carbonic anhydrase. Autoimmunity against carbonic anhydrase can result in cancer. Such cancers include acute myeloid leukemia, chronic lymphocytic leukemia, acute lymphocytic leukemia and gastric cancers (61).

[Adenovirus](#), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [ERVEBO Ebola vaccine](#), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep A ([Vaqta](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Japanese Encephalitis ([Ixiaro](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pneumovax](#) 13), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Polio (IPV – [Ipol](#)), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), [Smallpox](#) (Vaccinia) (ACAM2000), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#)), Varicella ([Varivax](#)), [Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax), Zoster (Shingles) ([Zostavax](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#)), Biologics

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Blood brain barrier (BBB) disruption

Polysorbate 80 (73) and glutamate receptor antibodies (27) can cause BBB disruption.

DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar 13](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Cardiac arrhythmia

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae*, Hepatitis B surface antigen, Influenza A, Hepatitis A and rubella protein contained in vaccines can cause cardiac arrhythmia. (74)

DT ([Sanofi](#)), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PevaxHIB](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep A ([Vaqta](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar 13](#)), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#))

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Cerebral folate deficiency syndrome

See vaccines listed under [autism](#).

Cerebral infarction

Autoimmunity induced by the following proteins in vaccines can result in cerebral infarction.

(41,42,75) *H. influenzae*, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae*, *C. tetani*, Hepatitis B surface antigen, cow's milk and Influenza A proteins.

[Adenovirus](#), Anthrax ([Biothrax](#)), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar 13](#)), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Corn allergy

Excipients such as polysorbate 80 derived from corn can be the cause of corn allergy. (27,33,35,36,76)

DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar 13](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Crohn's disease

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae*, bovine, porcine, guinea pig, African green monkey and chick proteins contained in vaccines can cause Crohn's disease. (4)

[Adenovirus](#), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [ERVEBO Ebola vaccine](#), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep A ([Vaqta](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Hepelisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pneumovax 13](#)), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Polio (IPV – [Ipol](#)), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#)), Varicella ([Varivax](#)), [Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax), Zoster (Shingles) ([Zostavax](#)), Zoster (Shingles) (Shingrix), Biologics

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Diabetes mellitus

Yeast and animal proteins contained in vaccines can cause diabetes mellitus. (5)

See vaccines listed under [Cerebral infarction](#)

Egg allergy

Egg proteins contained in vaccines cause the development of egg allergy (33,35,36,76,77)

Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), [Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax), Zoster (Shingles) (Zostavax)

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Encephalitis

Injury listed in US National Vaccine Injury Compensation Program's Vaccine Injury Table, for the MMR vaccine. (18)

[MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad)

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Epilepsy

Plant proteins such as those derived from wheat, soy, peanut, sesame and corn, used in the manufacture of excipients such as polysorbate 80, can cause glutamate receptor autoimmunity related epilepsy. (27)

DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar 13](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Fibromyalgia

Plant proteins such as those derived from wheat, soy, peanut, sesame and corn, used in the manufacture of vaccine excipients such as polysorbate 80, can cause glutamate receptor autoimmunity related fibromyalgia. (27,78–80)

See vaccines listed under [Epilepsy](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Gelatin allergy

Gelatin protein contained in vaccines cause the development of gelatin allergy. (33,35,36,76,77,81–83)

[MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), Varicella ([Varivax](#)), [Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax), Zoster (Shingles) ([Zostavax](#))

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Glioma

The varicella vaccine prevents natural infection which protects against glioma (84).

[MMRV](#) (ProQuad), Varicella ([Varivax](#))

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Guillain-Barre syndrome (GBS)

Influenza vaccines cause the development of GBS. (18)

Also see vaccines listed under [Autoimmune diseases and cancer](#)

Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal

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Hypothyroidism

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae*, *S. Typhi* and Influenza A proteins contained in vaccines can cause the development of hypothyroidism. (49,53)

[DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pneumovax 13](#)), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#))

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD)

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis* and *S. cerevisiae* proteins contained in vaccines include residual catalase protein, an autoantigen in IBD. (7)

E. coli protein contained in vaccines and biologics (such as insulin injections (85,86)) can cause IBD. May be residual proteins from the manufacturing process (87) or a contaminant. (32)

[DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil](#) 9), [Humulin-R](#) (Insulin), [LANTUS](#) (Insulin), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Prevnar](#) 13), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)).

In addition, see vaccines listed under [Crohn's Disease](#)

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Influenza allergy and influenza shock syndrome (ISS)

IgE mediated sensitization to influenza viral proteins in the influenza vaccine can cause influenza shock syndrome (ISS) upon subsequent influenza infections. (88)

Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal

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Intussusception

Rotavirus ([RotaTeq](#)), Rotavirus ([Rotarix](#)) (89,90)

Kawasaki disease

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae* and measles vaccines(51,91) include residual proteins with molecular mimicry to human HSP63 which is an autoantigen in Kawasaki disease. Influenza vaccines can also cause Kawasaki disease. (56)

[DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil](#) 9), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent,

Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), MMR (MMR-II), MMRV (ProQuad), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pneumovax](#)), Td (Tenivac), Td (Mass Biologics), Tdap (Adacel), Tdap (Boostrix).

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Maternal antibody related autism

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae*, Hepatitis B and measles vaccines include residual proteins with molecular mimicry to autoantigens involved in maternal antibody related autism. (44,45,92,93)

In addition, milk proteins contained in vaccines can cause [Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism](#). And plant proteins contained in vaccines can cause [Maternal glutamate receptor antibody related autism](#).

[DT \(Sanofi\)](#), [DTap \(Daptacel\)](#), [DTap \(Infanrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Kinrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Quadracel\)](#), [DTap HepB IPV \(Pedarix\)](#), [DTap IPV/Hib \(Pentacel\)](#), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), [Hib \(Hiberix\)](#), [Hib \(PedvaxHIB\)](#), [Hep B \(Engerix-B\)](#), [Hep B \(Recombivax\)](#), [Hep B \(Hepelisav-B\)](#), [Hep A/Hep B \(Twinrix\)](#), [Human Papillomavirus \(HPV\) \(Gardasil 9\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenACWY-Menactra\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenACWY-Menveo\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenB – Bexsero\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenB – Trumenba\)](#), [MMR \(MMR-II\)](#), [MMRV \(ProQuad\)](#), [MYXREDLIN \(Insulin\)](#), [Novolin \(Insulin\)](#), [Novolog \(Insulin\)](#), [OZEMPIC injection](#), [Pneumococcal \(PCV13 – Prevnar 13\)](#), [Pneumococcal \(PPSV-23 – Pneumovax\)](#), [Td \(Tenivac\)](#), [Td \(Mass Biologics\)](#), [Tdap \(Adacel\)](#), [Tdap \(Boostrix\)](#)

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Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism

Caused by the following vaccines that contain milk proteins.

[Anthrax \(Biothrax\)](#), [Adenovirus](#), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), [DTap \(Daptacel\)](#), [DTap \(Infanrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Kinrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Quadracel\)](#), [DTap HepB IPV \(Pedarix\)](#), [DTap IPV/Hib \(Pentacel\)](#), [ActHiB](#), [Hib \(Hiberix\)](#), [Td \(Tenivac\)](#), [Td \(Mass Biologics\)](#), [Tdap \(Adacel\)](#), [Tdap \(Boostrix\)](#), [Typhoid \(Typhim Vi\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenACWY-Menactra\)](#), [Pneumococcal \(PCV13 – Prevnar 13\)](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Maternal glutamate receptor antibody related autism

See vaccines listed under [Epilepsy](#)

Membranous Nephropathy

Membranous nephropathy is caused by bovine serum albumin (BSA) contained in vaccines (94,95).

[Adenovirus](#), DT ([Sanofi](#)), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hep A ([Vaqta](#)), Japanese Encephalitis ([Ixiaro](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar](#) 13), Polio (IPV – [Ipol](#)), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim](#) Vi), Varicella ([Varivax](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Zostavax](#))

Milk Allergy

Cow's milk proteins contained in vaccines cause the development of milk allergy. (35,36,76,77)

See vaccines listed under [Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Narcolepsy

Influenza virus proteins (96) animal and yeast proteins contained in vaccines, cause narcolepsy. (53)

DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), Hep B ([Engerix](#)-B), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav](#)-B), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil](#) 9), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Pevnar](#) 13),

Also see vaccines listed under [Atopic dermatitis](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Neurodegenerative disorders

See vaccines listed under [Epilepsy](#)

Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD)

Animal proteins contained in vaccines cause NMOSD. (4,5,47,97)

Also see vaccines listed under [Autoimmune diseases and cancer](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Neuropsychiatric disorders

See vaccines listed under [Epilepsy](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Obesity

See vaccines listed under [Cerebral Infarction](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Optic Ischemic Neuropathy

Optic Ischemic Neuropathy is an adverse event observed during clinical trials of the Shingrix vaccine (48,98).

Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS)

See vaccines listed under [Maternal folate receptor alpha antibody related autism](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Rheumatoid arthritis

See vaccines listed under [Autoimmune diseases and cancer](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

Rice Allergy

Rice proteins contained in the vaccine causes the development of rice allergy (64).

[ERVEBO Ebola vaccine](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Shingles

The varicella vaccine causes loss of natural exposure to the chicken pox virus and loss of natural immune boosting. The result is increased risk of shingles (99).

[MMRV](#) (ProQuad), Varicella ([Varivax](#))

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Soy allergy

Soy derived polysorbate 80 and soy proteins contained in vaccines cause the development of soy allergy. (27,33,35,36,76)

DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediarix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Prevnar 13](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Sub-acute Sclerosing Panencephalitis (SSPE)

The measles live virus vaccine can cause SSPE. (100)

[MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS)

H. influenzae, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae* and Hepatitis B surface antigen contained in vaccines can cause SIDS. (50,51)

[DT \(Sanofi\)](#), [DTap \(Daptacel\)](#), [DTap \(Infanrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Kinrix\)](#), [DTap IPV \(Quadracel\)](#), [DTap HepB IPV \(Pediatrix\)](#), [DTap IPV/Hib \(Pentacel\)](#), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), [Hib \(Hiberix\)](#), [Hib \(PedvaxHIB\)](#), [Hep B \(Engerix-B\)](#), [Hep B \(Recombivax\)](#), [Hep B \(Hepelisav-B\)](#), [Hep A/Hep B \(Twinrix\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenACWY-Menactra\)](#), [Meningococcal \(MenACWY-Menveo\)](#), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, [Pneumococcal \(PCV13 – Prevnar 13\)](#), [Pneumococcal \(PPSV-23 – Pneumovax\)](#)

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Supraventricular tachyarrhythmia

Supraventricular tachyarrhythmia is a serious adverse event observed during clinical trials of the Shingrix vaccine. (48)

Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Supraventricular tachycardia

Supraventricular tachycardia is a serious adverse event observed during clinical trials of the Shingrix vaccine. (48)

Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#))

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Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE)

Yeast proteins contained in vaccines can cause SLE. (43,53)

See vaccines listed under [Atopic dermatitis](#)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Type 1 diabetes (T1D)

Type 1 diabetes can be caused by bovine insulin present in vaccines manufactured using cow's milk proteins. (77) T1D can also be caused by animal proteins, (4,5,17,26) Polysorbate 80 (27), *H. influenzae*, *S. pneumoniae*, *C. diphtheriae*, *B. pertussis*, *C. tetani*, *N. meningitidis*, *S. cerevisiae*, Hepatitis B surface antigen, Influenza A and measles proteins contained in vaccines. (5) Rotavirus vaccines may also induce T1D. (101)

Anthrax ([Biothrax](#)), [Adenovirus](#), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [ERVEBO Ebola vaccine](#), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hib ([PedvaxHIB](#)), Hep A ([Havrix](#)), Hep A ([Vaqta](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil](#) 9), Influenza ([Afluria](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluad](#)), Influenza ([Fluarix](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flublok](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Flulaval](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluvirin](#)), Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Quadrivalent, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) High Dose, Influenza ([Fluzone](#)) Intradermal, Japanese Encephalitis ([Ixiaro](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Bexsero](#)), Meningococcal (MenB – [Trumenba](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Prevnar](#) 13), Pneumococcal (PPSV-23 – [Pneumovax](#)), Polio (IPV – [Ipol](#)), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), Rotavirus ([RotaTeq](#)), Rotavirus ([Rotarix](#)) [Smallpox](#) (Vaccinia) (ACAM2000), Td ([Tenvac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#)), Varicella ([Varivax](#)), [Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax), Zoster (Shingles) ([Zostavax](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#)), Biologics

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Vitiligo

Animal or yeast proteins contained in vaccines cause the development of vitiligo. (4,5)

[Adenovirus](#), [DT \(Sanofi\)](#), DTap ([Daptacel](#)), DTap ([Infanrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Kinrix](#)), DTap IPV ([Quadracel](#)), DTap HepB IPV ([Pediatrix](#)), DTap IPV/Hib ([Pentacel](#)), [ERVEBO Ebola vaccine](#), [FIASP](#) (Insulin), [Prevnar 13](#), [ActHiB](#), Hib ([Hiberix](#)), Hep A ([Vaqta](#)), Hep B ([Engerix-B](#)), Hep B ([Recombivax](#)), Hep B ([Heplisav-B](#)), Hep A/Hep B ([Twinrix](#)), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) ([Gardasil 9](#)), Influenza ([Flucelvax](#)) Trivalent & Quadrivalent, Japanese Encephalitis ([Ixiaro](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menactra](#)), Meningococcal (MenACWY-[Menveo](#)), [MMR](#) (MMR-II), [MMRV](#) (ProQuad), [MYXREDLIN](#) (Insulin), [Novolin](#) (Insulin), [Novolog](#) (Insulin), [OZEMPIC](#) injection, Pneumococcal (PCV13 – [Prevnar 13](#)), Polio (IPV – [Ipol](#)), Rabies ([RabAvert](#)), [Smallpox](#) (Vaccinia) (ACAM2000), Td ([Tenivac](#)), Td ([Mass Biologics](#)), Tdap ([Adacel](#)), Tdap ([Boostrix](#)), Typhoid ([Typhim Vi](#)), Varicella ([Varivax](#)), [Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax), Zoster (Shingles) ([Zostavax](#)), Zoster (Shingles) ([Shingrix](#)),
Biologics

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

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Wheat allergy

Polysorbate 80 in vaccines can contain wheat proteins as polysorbate 80 is derived from plant proteins including wheat. (27,35,36,76)

See [Epilepsy](#)

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[Disease list](#)

Yellow fever vaccine-associated viscerotropic disease

Yellow fever vaccine can cause viscerotropic disease. (102)

[Yellow Fever](#) (YF-Vax)

[Vaccines and Biologics list](#)

[Disease list](#)

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